

Effect of Fiber-Reinforcement on Mechanical Properties of Self-Consolidating Concrete for Transportation Infrastructure Applications

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ABSTRACT

Self-Consolidating Concrete (SCC), also known as self-compacting concrete, is a type of hydraulic cement concrete that easily forms around the reinforcement without segregation. Design of an SCC mix is chosen based on either powder-type, viscosity modifying admixture-type, or a mixture of the two types depending on structural and constructional conditions, and materials available. Due to the improved fresh properties of SCC, this concrete type is more favorable for precast sections that could be used in transportation infrastructure applications. The main objective of this study was to investigate the application of fiber-reinforced SCC in transportation infrastructures. The use of sustainable non-cementitious materials and recycled fibers in the SCC mix, affect the compressive strength, tensile strength and crack initiation and propagation. The improved mechanical properties of the modified SCCs make them alternative solutions for precast sections for transportation infrastructure applications compared to the conventional concrete.

INTRODUCTION

Self-consolidating concrete has been used in a variety of mass construction applications and structural implementation such as tunnels, dams, bridge decks and other such projects. Many studies have been conducted around the world to evaluate the mechanical properties of SCC that are of interest for a variety of reasons. The concern is more so with the application in transportation infrastructures which require the workability and passing ability of concrete without in-situ vibration. There is also an emphasis on the study of fiber reinforcement in these mixes and how this affects fresh and hardened properties of SCC. Design of an SCC mix is chosen based on either powder-type, viscosity modifying admixture-type, or a mixture of the two types depending on structural and constructional conditions, and availability of materials (Ouchi, 2003). SCC mixes have undergone several alterations and as shown in the literature can have discrepancies between

the origin of their applications, specifically in Japan, Europe and the United States where arguably the most amount of research on this subject has been conducted.

An SCC mix is typically characterized by the conventional ingredients that make up regular concrete. The main difference is in the inclusion of admixtures such as viscosity modifying admixture (VMA), and high range water-reducing (HRWR) agent as well as superplasticizers (SP). Aside from these, minor differences in aggregates used such as crushed limestone, gravel, sand and other types of materials, coupled with alterations in proportioning, had several varying effects on the properties of SCC. Likewise, some of the studies in the literature evaluated the effects of air entrainment on these mixes, in one study coupling them with the admixtures to extensively display these effects (Khayat and Roussel, 1999).

Normally for SCC with high water-powder ratio and/or low powder content, VMA is added to improve mix stability by enhancing rheological properties and reducing segregation. HRWR is an agent used to reduce water content and produce better flow ability. The properties the agent typically affects are prolonging setting time, slump and air entrainment depending on the dosage used. Such an agent, when used in conjunction with VMA for example, can achieve greater workability for SCC. There are different types of HRWR to address their desired performance goals and correct any shortcomings of the designed SCC. Superplasticizers of poly-carboxylic ether type were also utilized to achieve workability targets; such was used to complement VMA, HRWR or a combination of all three. In addition to these three typical chemical admixtures used, air-entraining admixture (AEA,) while not being widely implemented, also serves a role in some SCC mix designs mostly for increasing freezing resistance of the concrete, increasing cohesion, and improving compaction in mixes with lower workability. Table 1 summarizes the application of different additives in SCC mixes across the literature.

Geopolymer is another specialized type of SCC which is characterized by alkali-activation to form a binder which holds the aggregates and other cementitious materials together. Geopolymer SCC has been mostly found to have greater than and equal strength compared to Portland Cement concrete as well as better Sulphate, fire and acid resistance to name a few properties. Such a concrete has been of interest to become a possible stronger alternative to conventional concrete types. The concrete was also reinforced with rebar and fibers in differing publications with related strengths and property changes. The main difference between the Geopolymer and normal concrete would be the need for an alkaline activator solution made up of varying ratios of certain chemicals. This activator reacts with the other component materials to create the paste which binds the aggregates together.

Both types of concrete were tested in a few rheological and mechanical tests to determine characteristics such as flow ability, setting, cohesion, aggregate segregation, and compressive strength. These tests have been split into the categories of fresh state and hardened state properties. Along with this, attention was paid to aspects such as water-cement or solid ratios across the literature.

Table 1- Admixture and Air Entrainment Characteristic across the Literature

Author of Paper	Air Entrainment (%)	AEA ¹	VMA ²	HRWR ³	SP ⁴
Abbasi, et al. (1999)	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
Khayat & Roussel (1999)	5.1, 5.7, 7.1, 7.9 after 60 min 4.8, 4.9, 5.8, 5.9	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Holschemacher & Klug (2002)	>5%	Yes	No	No	Yes
Ouchi et al. (2003)	4.5-7%	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
C. I. Goodier (2003)	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
Corinaldesi & Moriconi (2003)	2.9	No	Yes	No	Yes
P.L. Domone (2005)	No	Yes	No	No	No
Domone (2006)	No	No	No	No	Yes
Ferrara et al. (2007)	No	No	No	No	Yes
Rangan (2008)	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Pintado & Barragan (2009)	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
Guneyisi (2009)	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
Bamonte & Gambarova (2012)	No	No	No	No	Yes
Khaloo et al. (2013)	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
Singh et al. (2015)	No	No	No	No	Yes
Ramujee & PothaRaju (2016)	No	No	No	No	Yes
Hardjito et al. (2017)	No	No	No	Yes	No

¹AEA – air entrainment admixture, ²VMA – viscosity modifying admixture, ³HRWR – high-range water reducing agent, ⁴SP – superplasticizer

SCC Fresh and Hardened Properties

Aside from the conventional slump flow test, there are a set of specialized tests to evaluate the filling ability, workability and passing ability of SCC. For the slump flow test, many times shown as T_50 or some other variation in the literature, from the initial point of release of the cone to when the concrete ceases to spread outward onto the floor or testing surface the time is measured and recorded (ASTM 1611). More specifically, the J-Ring slump is a rigid ring with 300 mm in diameter and supported 100 mm above the floor or surface by 16 mm wide reinforcement rods. The rods are spaced apart to allow for the SCC poured in to pass through and enable the operator to record both change in diameter and height. The change in diameter is in comparison to the results obtained from the J-Ring test (ASTM C 1621) and the slump diameter test. This comparison

shows how restrictive the passage of SCC is when put through the rods as opposed to the slump diameter test which has no objects that congest the flow. The results also display how viscous the SCC is and if aggregate segregation occurs. The change in height comes from measuring the height of the fresh concrete inside of the ring and outside of it. The higher the difference, the lower the passing ability, as the test clearly shows the inability of the concrete to pass through the rods and out of the inner ring (Figure 1c).

The column segregation test (ASTM C 1610), gives an estimate of the segregation and resistance exhibited by the mix. With a 203.2 mm diameter, the column is a PVC pipe split up into three sections that are initially clamped together. SCC concrete is poured into the pipe and left for 15 minutes, afterward which the sections are individually removed, and the concrete washed over a sieve retaining the coarse aggregates. These aggregates are dried and measured by mass for each section, from which the coefficient of variation is calculated, and the segregation resistance is estimated (Figure 1d).

The L-box fill test also works to measure passing and filling ability (Figure 1b). The equipment is in the shape of an L with a hollow vertical portion that connects to a hollow horizontal portion with a gate opening to allow the fresh concrete to pass through reinforcement bars similar to those described in the J-Ring test. The concrete, initially poured into the vertical portion, is released and flows through the bars at which point it is timed for when it reaches 200 mm, 400 mm and once it halts motion. From this point, the height at which the concrete stops flowing into the horizontal and that which is left inside the vertical are recorded to produce the blocking ratio. Similarly, the U-type fill test has equipment that is in the shape of a U and has fresh concrete poured into one side of the apparatus. A gate located symmetrically in the middle of the curved bottom portion which is released and allows the concrete to flow through bars on the other side of the gate. From the point of release the concrete is timed until it stops flowing into the other side. Heights on either side are taken and the ratio is estimated (European Guidelines 2005). Both tests can also be used to measure segregation in a similar manner to the J-Ring test.

The V-funnel test (Figure 1a) is a system which has a V-shaped funnel that has a small opening at the bottom and is used to evaluate SCC with max aggregate size of 20 mm. The funnel is filled with 12 liters of the fresh concrete and is timed from the point it is released and flows out of the funnel. It is then refilled, this time with the concrete being allowed to set for 5 minutes and timed in the same manner. The comparison of the times displays whether there is segregation in the mix as well as paste viscosity (European Guidelines 2005).

Hardened properties are tested after the fresh concrete is compacted and cast into cylinders, prisms or some other standard-specific geometric shape for later testing. Curing for SCC cylinders undergoes the similar procedure described for conventional vibrated concrete (CVC) (Morcoux, 2016). It is therefore characterized by placement into plastic or similar material cylinders that can assure there is no water evaporation from the fresh concrete after finishing. These are stored afterward and allowed to set for either 24 +/- 8 hours, 20 +/- 4 hours for prolonged setting mixes or determined by ASTM C403/C403M. After this setting and subsequent hardening they are removed and cured at 23 +/- 2 degrees Celsius either in a misting room, water tanks or some other

sort of system to maintain surface moisture of the specimens. The first 48 hours they are to be cured in a non-vibrating environment and depending on the specifications or criteria of the experimenter left until they are to be tested.

Figure 1. Tests for estimation of SCC fresh properties, a) V-Funnel, b) L-Box, c) J-Ring, and d) Segregation Column

The hardened properties that were examined in the literature range from compressive strength values to flexural and splitting tensile strength to modulus of elasticity or a combination of all these. The compression strength results were of particular interest and taken at 28 days. However, it could also be seen that some authors took results at even wider ranges, for example at 7, 14, 21, 56 and even 91 days (Ouchi 2003). The compression test is comprised of loading cylinders, blocks or other concrete sample shapes into a machine that with or without proper

capping procedures presses vertically into the specimen loading it gradually. The loading continues until the specimen fails and results are recorded. The splitting tensile strength test also works in a similar system with primarily a cylinder being loaded sideways into a metal mold in the shape of a triangle with a base plate and a long rectangular piece of plywood or other material spanning the length of the specimen. The rectangular portion compress into the cylinder until failure in the form of cracking or the specimen being split in half. The studies in the literature gave some correlation between mix compositions to the recorded properties of the SCC specimens and observed some trends with proportioning and/or inclusion of additional materials such as admixtures or fibers.

Figure 2 summarizes the properties of SCCs across the literature. Water-Cement ratio is one of main factors that affect the compressive strength of the SCC. Reviewing the information across the literature showed that a ratio of 0.4 is more common in the SCC mix design. A few other studies showed that the ratio of 0.5 or in some cases 0.2 was used for the mix proportioning. The distribution 28-day compressive strength of SCC samples also showed that majority of the studies in the literature reported a compressive strength of 40 MPa or more. However, it seems that adding fibers to the mix and in some cases, using recycled non-cementitious materials (i.e. fly ash or blast furnace slag) improved the hardened properties in terms of compressive strength.

Figure 2 – Distribution of a) W/C ratio and b) 28-day compressive strength for SCC mixes across the literature

Application of SCC and Fiber-Reinforced SCC in Transportation Infrastructures

Fiber-reinforced SCCs have been evaluated in a number of studies in the literature. It also has been implemented and evaluated in some transportation infrastructure applications. The following sections summarize the relevant studies in the literature.

Boulekbache et al. (2010) investigated in the flow ability of fiber-reinforced concrete and the effect of fibers on mechanical properties of SCC. In general, adding fibers to the mix decreases the drying shrinkage and propagation of micro cracks while enhancing fatigue and impact resistance. They used a fluid model to simulate and estimate the orientation and distribution of fibers in the mix. However, based on the experimental work in that study, the addition of fibers slightly decreased the compressive strength of the SCC mixes. On the other hand, the ductility and

flexural strength were improved in the fiber-reinforced SCC. Also, the fiber orientation seemed to impact the flexural capacity in terms of initiation and propagation of micro cracks.

Khaloo et al. (2014) studied the performance of fiber-reinforced SCC using steel fibers. They have performed a series of laboratory tests to evaluate the fresh and hardened properties of SCC mixes containing different dosage of steel fibers. The addition of 2% fiber by volume of the mix, decreased the workability and passing ability through the J-ring rebars. It also slightly decreased the compressive strength by about 2% compared to the SCC mixes without fibers. However, both split tensile strength and flexural strength of the fiber-reinforced SCC were increased compared to the plain samples. The flexural toughness also increased by increasing the volume of fibers in the SCC mix.

Figure 3 compares the finished surface condition of two tunnel lining elements constructed with conventional concrete (Figure 1a) and self-compacting concrete (Figure 1b) as documented in Hulin et al. (2011). Two types of SCC mixes using polypropylene and steel fibers were designed and proportioned for this study. The higher workability, passing ability and flowability of the SCC mixes were beneficial to produce a smoother surface for liner segments while achieving a high compressive strength (Hulin et al. 2011).

Figure 3 – Comparison of finished concrete surface for a tunnel liner element for a) conventional concrete, and b) self-compacting concrete (Hulin et al. 2011)

Schumacher (2006) studied the rotation capacity of tunnel liners constructed with steel fiber-reinforced SCC. That study found that using SCC prevents localization of cracks in structural elements. The addition of steel fibers increased the confinement capacity and tension stiffening of the pre-cast liner elements. For bending members with steel fibers in the mix, the load bearing capacity was observed to be higher compared to conventional concrete.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

A review of studies conducted on self-compacting concrete's fresh and hardened properties were observed. The purpose of the review was to study the properties of these concretes for proposed applications in transportation infrastructures and other relevant uses related to fiber-reinforcement. Points of particular interest were in found in the variation of water-cement (w/c) ratios, admixtures

and other mix parameters such as fiber content and fly ash by the differing authors. Trends and other interesting findings are listed below.

Two of the most highly regarded and documented areas of interest for the review were the differences in both w/c ratio and fiber content. The w/c ratios seen mostly across the literature were around 0.35-0.4 range and exhibited a multitude of compressive strengths ranging from 30-80 MPa. Ratios outside of this range were typically found to produce less than 60 MPa of compressive strength. For the studies specifically related to fiber entrainment we see a few trends when regarding alterations as listed below:

- Increasing fiber content increased compressive strength at constant w/c
- W/C ratios affected the strength of mixes more so than fiber content
- Long term strength in studies carried out with fiber content produced good long-term strength in mixes
- fiber reinforced SCC was highly flowable and cohesive, having high slump flow and developing compressive strength and flexural toughness similar to regular concrete

Likewise, the review also focused on the effects of admixtures used in the various designs. Such are detailed as superplasticizer, high-range water reducing agent (HRWR) and viscosity modifying admixture (VMA), of which each were either chosen to stand alone or in combination with the others. Along with these a less widely implemented by observed admixture used was that of AEA or air-entraining admixture. Conclusions reached by analyzing the literature and comparing trends showed that:

- Mixes using superplasticizer alone were higher than mixes that incorporated VMA, HRWR or a combination of all three admixtures
- VMA had the largest effect on the strength of the mixes when added
- AEA served the purpose of increasing freezing resistance of the concrete, increasing cohesion, and improving compaction in mixes with lower workability
- For high water-powder ratio and/or low powder content, VMA was added to improve mix stability by enhancing rheological properties and reducing segregation
- Superplasticizers of poly-carboxylic ether type or otherwise specified were also utilized achieve workability targets
- HRWR was used to reduce water content and produce better flow ability

Other than the aforementioned mix parameters alterations to fly-ash content were the only major component of mix design which was observed. Findings included the following:

- Fly ash was observed to decrease both flow time and compressive strength
- No discernable effect was produced through the different classes of fly ash used in mix designs
- Optimum fly ash content in regards to trade-offs between strength, durability and longer setting times was found to be closer to smaller doses
- With regards to geopolymers, low calcium fly ash was used instead of higher concentration amounts because it might affect the polymerization and change the microstructure

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